

Session 1: Discussions on Benefit/Cost Dimensions

Benefits of energy project:

- Industrialization -> factories (higher potential for growth), more employment, exports
- Industry generates higher GDP per capita, especially if the factories are food-processing based on corn.
- Industry growth will contain the population fertility rate-> since agriculture is limited land, whereas industry has expansion potential
- Diversification of the economy-> reduced economic risk
- Raising the education and skills level of the country
- Energy and electricity will have positive spill-over effects for more exports, starting point is a balanced BOT ($X=M$), now with energy we can enhance X , and therefore BOT+, GDP+.
- In the long run, locally produced energy and electricity will benefit the corn farmers-> agricultural mechanization and more efficient farming.
- More employment from the energy project-> added future consumption of food (including corn).
- Raising the standard of living in rural area-> roads and infrastructure will gradually be better, also better hospitals, and better schools.
- Energy project will increase Investment and Mexico will be more attractive for foreign investments as well-> "I"+, "G" (taxes component)+, hence GDP growth.
- Higher know-how (technology) in the economy with higher education/skills-> R&D and innovation in the economy.

Costs of energy project:

- Land lost due to the energy excavation-> output lost-> lower GDP
- Pollution -> health costs to be paid by already low-wage farmers
- If minimum scale of energy output is not attained, this will create net economic loss.
- Erosion and depletion of soil fertility-> agricultural output (-), GDP (-), and raise in unemployment
- Community resistance-> project default and social uproar, political instability, riots-> discouraging Investments
- Less exports of agricultural corn
- Imports of machinery for the power plant, especially if equipment and technology is imported
- Opportunity cost of using local energy instead of exporting ($FOB > \text{local price}$)
- Poverty might increase in the short term-> less land, structural unemployment (mis-match between farm skills and industry/energy skills).
- Equipment depreciates faster than land -> land is more "asset valuable" for the economy? -> industry is more financial risk-> raise the country risk

Session 2: Discussions on Strategies

How (strategies) with eye on target that economic benefits will overcome costs (non-technical)?

- Employment: local skilled employment, foreign outsourcing for training the skills at the beginning of the project, use “appropriate technology” that matches the trained skills.
- Location: locate energy project in land areas that are less fertile, location should be furthest from high population areas.
- Community resistance: offer payments in exchange for displacement, accelerate social benefits for the most vulnerable groups (free education, added health benefits), town hall meetings face to face with leaders of families/tribes using a negotiation expert
- Trade impacts: raising infrastructure and reduce transport costs, decrease interest rate for export investments, exporting the food processing output.
- Investment: electricity and infrastructure are “necessary but not enough (not sufficient)”-> we need to allow free capital flow, better investment procedures, reducing taxes, less corruption, and less monopoly power and consequently less barriers to entry.
- Scale of Output: use other country experiences comparable to Mexico to forecast the output expansion and the needed scale -> not go into any industry, but specialization into industries that have economies of scale (e.g., automotive, steel, cement, petrochemicals, etc.), Also, giving access to cheaper raw materials with adequate quality.
- Poverty: food subsidies in the short term to absorb the short-term poverty impacts, but in long-run these food subsidies should be lifted.

Mexico Energy Project- Answers to Technical Questions

1) Financial NPV:

MARR = 7.75% (risk adjusted)

$$\text{NPV} = -150\text{m} + 27.5\text{m} (P|A, 7.75\%, 10) = \boxed{\$36.6\text{m}}$$

↓
(x 6.7864)

Note: $(P|A, 7.75\%, 10) = \frac{(1+i)^n - 1}{i(1+i)^n} = 6.7864$

2) True Economic Cost:

Local price = \$65; true economic cost = $\frac{\text{financial}}{1-0.39} = \boxed{\$106.55}$

- Local price is subsidized to contain inflation, since energy is used in all economy sectors, including transport of agricultural and industrial goods.

3) Shadow Price of Energy:

Financial price = \$65 < FOB price (\$112); whereas CIF price (\$118) > \$65 financial price.

- Energy is considered an “exportable” commodity in this project.
 - If energy is exported, it will give higher returns to the economy (FOB>local).
 - If energy is imported, it will be more expensive (CIF>local).
- Shadow price = FOB exportable price = $\boxed{\$112 / \text{unit}}$. Why? Because this is the lost economic opportunity at which energy could have been exported at \$112/unit, instead of used locally. Note that importing energy is more expensive, so there is no opportunity cost in importing.

4) Mexico’s SDR:

SDR. Use LIBOR (12 month UK £ ; 0.962% / year) plus County Risk factor.

From OECD tables, Mexico has risk rating of x3 (1 → 7). So, it is an average risk economy.

SDR reasonable estimate = LIBOR + 3xLIBOR = $\boxed{3.848\% / \text{year}}$. This replaces the interest rate.

5) Why SDR is Low:

SDR < MARR to account for economic value-added to the long-run development impact of the project. In addition, a low SDR values future generations and their right in reaping the benefits of a long-run development project.

6) Economic NPV:

$$\text{Annual Economic Returns} = \text{financial} \times \left[\frac{\text{opp. cost of energy extraction}}{\text{true economic cost of the energy resource}} \right]$$

Sustainability criterion, "Hartwick model"

$$= \$27.5m \times \frac{\$112 / \text{unit}}{\$106.55 / \text{unit}} = \boxed{\$28.9m \text{ per year.}}$$

$$\text{Economic NPV} = \boxed{\$86.24m} > \text{financial NPV}$$

- Financial NPV underestimates value-added of the energy project to the economy.
- This is due to the expected positive spill-over impact of energy to other sectors, including industrialization, long-run technological effects, and GDP growth developmental impacts.

7) Mexico's SER and Currency Valuation:

Official exchange rate = 19.08 pesos / \$

$$SER = \text{Official Exchange Rate} \times \left(\frac{M + CO}{X + CI} \right)$$

Capital account = Capital Inflows – Capital Outflows = CI – CO

Since there is a "deficit of 24m" → Capital Account = -24m = CI – CO

This implies, -24m = \$551m – CO → CO = \$575m

$$\text{Therefore, } SER = 19.08 \times \frac{40,764m + 575m}{39,177m + 551m} = \boxed{19.85 \text{ pesos/\$}}$$

19.85 pesos/\$ is “shadow exchange” relative to 19.08 pesos/\$ “official exchange”

→ official exchange rate is over-appreciated, possibly due to internal politics to contain inflation. This is an example of economic policy: “inflation targeting”. Making the currency stronger reduces the price of imports, hence reducing inflation, and this enhances quality of life of Mexican citizens.

8) Minimum Wage:

To calculate the minimum wage:

$$\text{min. wage} = \frac{28,275 \text{ pesos / yr}}{19.85 \rightarrow \text{SER}} = \boxed{\$1424.4/\text{year}}$$

National average (PPP GDP per capita) is \$19.5K / year (note that the min wage < 1/10th of average wage in the country).

- This implies extreme inequality; and high poverty rate 46% even with minimum wage.
→ This is also connected to “over-appreciation”. How? Over-appreciation of currency limits the potential for exports, and makes imports less costly. This creates competitive pressure on domestic investment, hence business will be reluctant to give high wages. Yet, this policy also limits inflation, and containing inflation seems to be a strategic target for Mexico.

9) Labor VMP and Relative Productivity Index:

It is given that Mexico PPP GDP per capita = \$19.5K/year = National Average

	Agriculture “Traditional”	Industry “Modern”	Services
RP →	0.29	1.31	1.03

$$\text{RP (Sector)} = \frac{\% \text{ GDP value}}{\% \text{ Employment}}$$

Relative Productivity Index
(sector productivity relative to the national average)

The RP Table suggests the following:

- the relative productivity of agriculture is 0.29 (it is significantly lower than the national average).
- the services sector is equivalent to the national average (1.03 relative productivity).
- the relative productivity of industry is 1.31 (it is the most productive sector with significantly higher productivity than the national average).

Therefore, using national average as \$19.5K/yr as given by PPP GDP per capita in the case:

VMP_{skilled} (modern) → such as energy project

→ $1.311 \times \$19.5K / \text{year} = \$25.56K / \text{year}$ → “fair wage” of skilled worker

VMP_{unskilled} (traditional) → such as Agriculture e.g. corn

→ $0.29 \times \$19.5K / \text{year} = \$5.655K / \text{year}$ → “fair wage” of unskilled worker

Unskilled workers are more productive than minimum wage, hence they deserve it and more! (\$5.65K/year > min. wage of \$1.4K).

→ It is known that Mexican workers are one of the “hardest workers” worldwide.

10) Employment Generation:

Total Employment Generation (estimate):

- Direct (Jobs Created): 112 → primary
- Indirect Jobs = $112 \times 3 = 336$ → secondary
- Subtotal (Direct + Indirect) = 448 jobs → primary + secondary
- Induced (tertiary) = Subtotal $\times 8 = 3,584$ jobs → tertiary macro “ripple effect”
- Temporary 20% = $0.2 \times 448 = 90$ → temporary
- Informal 15% = $0.15 \times 448 = 67$ → informal
- Total = 4,189 jobs → Total Employment Generation